

INFLUENCING E-CAR DRIVING THROUGH SOUND DESIGN: EXPERIMENTING WITH HARMONICITY AND RHYTHM

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ABSTRACT

This study explored how additional auditory feedback in the interior of e-cars can convey vehicle-related information and influence driving behavior, with a focus on promoting economical driving. In an initial online test, seven sounds were integrated into a short video and assessed for emotional impact, sound perception, and information clarity. Based on the results, the sounds were refined and interactively tested in a modified game serving as a driving simulator. The study found a preference for static and harmonic sounds and showed influences on driving behavior through interactive sound.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the rise of electric vehicles, the interior soundscape of cars is changing. Unlike combustion engines, which provide drivers with feedback on the vehicle's condition, electric engines leave a gap in auditory information, and allow for a conscious design of the information content [1]. This study explores how additional interior auditory feedback can convey vehicle-related information and influence driving behavior, with a focus on promoting economical driving.

Two main motivations drive this research: Evidently, the ecological framework conditions are forcing us to save energy today, also in e-car driving, i.e. with users who are already concerned with environmental impact and thus potentially open to such feedback. In addition, range is an important factor for electric cars, and it therefore makes sense to support drivers in adopting an energy-saving driving style.

Conventional, commercially available feedback systems for energy consumption include visual feedback, both during the journey via a display as well as subsequently via the analysis of the data, as well as haptic feedback via a so-called eco-pedal. With this pedal, resistance can be felt when the vehicle is moved outside the economical range [2]. The obvious advantage of auditory feedback over visual feedback when driving is that you don't have to take your eyes off the road, which increases safety [3]. In comparison to haptic feedback, it can be argued that auditory

feedback has a higher information capacity.

The influencing of behaviour has been explored in various contexts under the notion of persuasive design [4]. In persuasive design, intelligent systems and environments are used to influence people in their actions or attitudes. For such a design to be accepted, sympathy and accessibility of the design are pre-conditions, while fascination, the promise of image enhancement, or the connection to others can be possible levers to use it. In general, moral questions regarding the responsibility for the actions triggered by persuasive design must be considered [5]. Early evaluation is particularly relevant in this case as, for example, warning noises can quickly be misinterpreted as criticism and may lead to unwanted actions [6].

Changing individual sound parameters can cause significant changes in perception, for instance quieter driving noises of combustion engine cars lead to the driving speed being perceived as slower [7]. The same authors cite that, when a person has already gained driving experience with a specific car, the vehicle sound can be used to estimate the speed. It has also been shown that a low background noise in the vehicle is perceived as comfortable, however, the absence of noise or auditory feedback leads to drivers having difficulties maintaining speed [2].

In this paper we describe a creative approach to interactive sound design that aimed at exploring factors such as harmonicity and rhythmicity for persuasive design in e-car driving. It was developed in a Master's thesis at the Institute of Electronic Music and Acoustics, University of Music and Performing Arts Graz, Austria. In this paper, we will first give a background on the interior soundscape of an e-car, and then discuss the chosen sound designs and their evaluation.

2. BACKGROUND

One main difference between the combustion engine and electric driving in terms of energy consumption is recuperation. Recuperation allows the energy released during acceleration to be largely recovered in e-cars, which is why gentle acceleration is far less decisive for low consumption in an electric car than it is in a combustion engine [8]. Therefore, speed and air resistance have most impact on energy consumption, and load-based feedback is less relevant for energy-efficient driving in e-cars. The most important factor for saving energy in e-cars therefore is slower driving.

The soundscape of a car is varied, and we regard it as

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a highly emotionally charged. Driving noise refers to all noises in the passenger compartment that directly correlate with the movement of the vehicle, and mainly consist of drive, rolling, and wind noise [9]. Active Sound Design can be added to the car's soundscape. As stated above, motor sounds of electric cars are much more silent than the ones of combustion vehicles. Therefore, the Acoustic Vehicle Alerting System (AVAS) has been introduced in order to warn pedestrians and other road users of the arrival of an e-car at speeds lower than 20 km/h. In the vehicle interior, Active Sound Design can be used to mask any background noise, to provide the necessary feedback on the vehicle's condition, and/or to trigger emotions or even for branding, i.e. the brand identity of a manufacturer, as discussed in [10]. These authors also mention the following key requirements for active sound design in the interior of an electric car: authenticity (the sounds should be evaluated as coming from the car), long-term usability (sounds should not tire or disturb even after a long period of use, but should remain interesting), and the clear difference to sounds of combustion engines.

A specific design challenge for e-cars is the fixed transmission ratio of an electric car: it has the effect of making the sound less varied than that of a combustion engine, as the gear changes always change the pitch [10]. For instance, narrow-band filtered noise has been suggested instead of using oscillators to achieve a more interesting sound texture [11]. For the presented project, the used sounds should offer reliable feedback on vehicle speed and put the driver in a stress-reduced and calm state. Taken together, these points should promote energy-saving driving behaviour.

3. SOUND DESIGN AND INITIAL LISTENING TEST

For our test design, we follow [1] in their first two steps, i.e. with a listening test and a subsequent test in a driving simulator. Complexity, immersion, and maturity of sounds increase from the first to the second test, while the variety of tested sounds decreases, and subjects have a different focus in these different test environments [12]. We chose a set of initial sound designs and evaluated their suitability in a first, online experiment.

3.1 Chosen sound designs

In general, the sounds needed to be designed to interactively reflect vehicle speed, i.e. respectively energy consumption. While noisy sounds are generated by the vehicles' rolling and wind noise, the added sounds should have tonal aspects to transport information via pitch. The same is true for combustion engine cars: there, the engine orders result from integer multiples of the ignition order (serving as fundamental frequency) and their distribution depends on the number of cylinders. These can be regarded as overtones of a sound. Consonant vibration ratios such as fifths and fourths are associated with rest and relaxation, and therefore preferred [13]. For our sound design, sounds were inspired by nature, starting for instance from

Figure 1. Spectrogram of the seven sounds used in experiment 1 and the added wind and roll noise. The spectrograms are generated with a window length of 0.03 s and the frequency range covers 0 – 10 kHz.

recordings of oceans' waves, while others were based on instruments such as the xylophone. We voluntarily experimented with harmonic vs. inharmonic sounds, and static vs. pulsating sounds. All sounds were created in the DAWs Cubase and Ableton. In the first experiment, the following seven sounds were used, as described below and shown in Fig. 1. Furthermore, Fig. 1(g) shows the wind and roll noise that has been added to all sounds for the evaluation. It has been designed using "Grip" by Boom Library.

- S1 A classic combustion sound referencing the "status quo", without gear-changing thus sounding more like an internal combustion engine idling. The Plugin "Igniter" by Krotos was used, which is based on granular synthesis.
- S2 A classic AVAS-sound found in electric vehicles. It was generated by stacking different waveforms.
- S3 An inharmonic version of the AVAS-sound S2. The overtones were shifted and 2 notes which are a tritone apart have been added.
- S4 A sound based on a singing bowl, a xylophone and a synthesizer pad. A generic sampler was used to form the percussive sounds into drones. The sound

should be reminiscent of meditation music. Here, only the formants were pitched, leading to persistent drone component of the sound.

- S5 An alternative version of S4 with standard pitch shifting.
- S6 A sound that should recall the sound and rhythmicity of oceans' waves. The recording of waves got filtered via Abletons "Resonator" Plugin.
- S7 An alternative version of S6, where also the speed of the waves' cycle is changing with the speed of the vehicle (the spectrogram being the same as S6).

3.2 Experiment 1: Online survey

For the online survey, a 44 second video of a car drive was combined with the different sounds. While the pitch was mapped to the estimated speed of the car, the volume got mapped to the estimated load. After each video, the participants were asked to fill out an online questionnaire. The conditions were fully randomized.

Twenty-six people took part in the study, half of whom stated their gender as female and the other half as male. The age distribution was as follows: 15 people 18-29 years, 5 people 30-39 years, 2 people 40-49 years, 4 people 50-59 years. All respondents have a driving license. Only one respondent stated that s/he frequently drove an electric car, 10 stated that they did so 'sometimes' and 15 stated that they never drove an electric car.

The questions comprised the general categorization of sounds, questions on subjective influence and information level, and free comments, as well as the emotional dimensions of valence, dominance and arousal [14]. For the latter, we included the original dimension of dominance, while many more recent publications include only valence and arousal to assess emotional impact, as also argued for by [15]. In our case of interactive driving behaviour, the perceived dominance of the sound design, ranging from obtrusive to unobtrusive, seemed to be a relevant factor. The sound categorization requested semantic differentials following adapted categories from [16, 17] on a 7-point Lickert scale: pleasant - unpleasant; quiet - loud; fine/smooth - rough/even; quiet/luxurious - dynamic/sporty; sharp - dull; and powerful - weak.

Shapiro-Wilk-Test showed that most data were not normally distributed. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test between pairs of sounds (S1-S2, S1-S3 etc.), with a significance level of $\alpha=0.05$, found significant differences for at least half of the sound pairs, for both valence (Tab. 1) and dominance (Tab. 2). Interestingly, for arousal nearly no significant differences showed up (Tab. 3).

Results of the sound categories helped us to understand the differences in perception between the sounds and update the sound quality. Also demographic-specific differences were recognised, for example women perceived sound 5 as significantly less boring. Results for emotional dimensions are shown in Fig. 2. They show that all sounds were rated as more or less obtrusive and with low valence, except for two sounds: the classical AVAS sound,

Figure 2. Graph of valence (high-low) and dominance (obtrusive-unobtrusive), giving results for both experiments (1 as black dots, 2 as grey squares) and all sounds as labelled (S1-S9).

Sound	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	0.011	0.042	0.190	0.782	0.622	0.341
2		<0.001	0.031	0.009	0.006	<0.001
3			0.004	0.010	0.008	0.095
4				0.192	0.351	0.023
5					0.874	0.286
6						0.089

Table 1. p-values for Wilcoxon signed-rank test for valence. Bold numbers for significant differences, where $p < 0.05$.

Sound	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	0.004	<0.001	0.848	0.008	0.309	0.035
2		<0.001	0.002	<0.001	0.007	<0.001
3			0.003	0.140	0.009	0.116
4				0.026	0.501	0.074
5					0.113	0.645
6						0.142

Table 2. p-values for dominance, same as Tab. 1.

Sound	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	0.572	0.445	0.568	0.049	0.130	0.111
2		0.620	0.953	0.163	0.062	0.093
3			0.686	0.479	0.401	0.377
4				0.147	0.114	0.154
5					0.879	0.947
6						0.647

Table 3. p-values for arousal, same as Tab. 1.

Figure 3. Setup of the driving simulator test.

S2, scored highest (while its inharmonic counterpart (S3) was rated worst); next-best was the meditation sound with drone tone, S4, and thus worth adapting it for further experiments.

Participants' familiarity with combustion engine sounds may have affected their perception. Some associated the combustion engine sound with idling or heavy vehicles, while frequent drivers of combustion cars were more likely to prefer this sound and refer to it as driving noise. Many participants found it difficult to imagine using our sounds in a real vehicle. The preference for harmonic, static sounds was observed, particularly for drone-based sounds, which were perceived as more pleasant. These findings go hand in hand with a recent and profound study on AVAS [18].

The free verbalization results also showed that some sounds failed to evoke the intended natural associations, specifically the wave-like sounds, that also scored rather low, and we thus decided not to use them further.

In general, there was only one significant difference between the sounds in the arousal category, so in this regard our subjects made no clear distinction between the sounds. Since arousal is often linked to the tempo of a music piece [19] and the used sounds were mostly drone sounds, we decided to add another sound variant with rhythm to the next experiment.

4. EXPERIMENT 2: DRIVING SIMULATOR

For the interactive setup, we partly re-designed the sounds and tested the following five sounds:

- 2-S2 The same AVAS sound as S2.
- 2-S3 The same inharmonic version as S3.
- 2-S4 A sound based on the meditation sounds S4 and S5.
- 2-S8 A rhythmic variant using the meditation sound 2-S4, playing a randomly repeating melody using a sampler with xylophone sounds.

- 2-S9 A variation of the melody of 2-S8 with more melodic variation.

4.1 Experiment design

For the second study, the video game 'BeamNG.drive'¹ was modded with our sounds. The game environment has realistic driving behaviour and a mode in which you drive an electric car on a set route where the consumption is calculated at the end. A Logitech steering wheel with associated pedals was used to make the driving feel more realistic. The setup is shown in Fig. 3. A demo video of the experiment setup is shown in <https://phaidra.kug.ac.at/o:135538>.

The downside of using BeamNG.drive as a base for the driving simulator was the limited control over the sound. While volumes between road-, wind- and engine-noise could be controlled in game, the game merely used samples for specific speeds, pitched them by changing playback speed and cross-faded between them. Therefore, we had limited influence on the pitch mapping. Furthermore, a filter to the overall sound is applied by the game, possibly to emulate the sound isolation from the chassis.

In a learning phase, each participant conducted a test drive with only wind and rolling noise in order to learn both controlling the simulator game and get to know the driving route. Then, the participants drove the same track one time with each sound, and subsequent to each track completed a questionnaire. The questions were adapted from the first experiment, though neglected sound categories now. The order of conditions was randomized between participants.

A total of 15 people took part in the second test, ten of whom were male and five female. As in the first trial, all participants had a driving licence. Four participants stated that they drove once a week or more often, the others once a month or less often. Nine participants never drive an electric car, while three drive an electric car sometimes or frequently.

4.2 Results

The statistical analysis was carried out as in experiment 1, but hardly any significant differences were found, which may be due to the smaller number of test subjects.

When analyzing the emotional response to the sounds, astonishingly, again, we found no significant difference between the sounds in terms of arousal. Results of the emotional dimensions valence and dominance are shown in Fig. 2 as grey squares. The sounds that had a correspondence in the first experiments all improved or stayed equal in valence and dominance ("improving" in dominance meaning here that it became less obtrusive). The meditation 2-S4 was, similar to the first experiment, relatively popular. The inharmonic 2-S3 was, as expected, less popular than its harmonic counterpart, 2-S2.

Results of total driving time and the remaining battery charge level after completing the test track are shown in Fig. 4. Sounds 2-S3 and 2-S8 have the longest median

¹ <https://www.beamng.com/game/>, last visited 03-2025

Figure 4. Boxplots showing the results for (a) the total driving time in minutes for the track and (b) the remaining battery charge level after completing the track, where 100% means full charge.

time to complete the track, 2-S8 has the least energy consumption (equals highest remaining battery charge level).

When asked for their long-term expectations, hardly any of the test participants could imagine using 2-S8 and 2-S9 as a driving sound.

Sound	2	3	4	5
1	0.154	0.232	0.002	0.001
2		0.001	0.103	0.127
3			0.002	0.003
4				0.627

Table 4. p-values for Wilcoxon signed-rank test for valence in experiment 2. Bold numbers for significant differences, where $p < 0.05$.

Sound	2	3	4	5
1	0.339	0.444	0.002	0.004
2		0.019	0.113	0.010
3			0.004	0.002
4				0.253

Table 5. p-values for dominance in experiment 2.

Sound	2	3	4	5
1	0.524	0.134	0.803	0.435
2		0.327	0.528	0.213
3			0.257	0.053
4				0.348

Table 6. p-values for arousal in experiment 2.

4.3 Conclusions from the driving simulator

The second experiment provided insights into the influence of different sounds on driving behavior and their acceptance as in-car auditory feedback. No significant differences were found in arousal levels, suggesting that rhythmicity alone does not affect perceived activation. The reason why 2-S8 and 2-S9 were so unpopular was likely due

to their association with warning signals in vehicles and their atonal nature caused by pitch shifts in response to speed changes. This pitch shift, caused by the implementation of the pitch shift in the game engine, led to possibly enervating glissandi, and constitutes a clear limitation in our test design. Maintaining a constant pitch may improve the acceptance in future studies.

Harmonic sounds like 2-S4 were preferred over inharmonic ones. Sound preference correlated with perceived speed estimation accuracy, indicating a link between auditory aesthetics and functionality. While 2-S8 led to lower energy consumption and longer driving times, it was perceived as obtrusive and undesirable. We hypothesize that this possibly caused drivers to slow down, in order to avoid unpleasant high-pitched tones, and thus indeed lead to lower energy consumption.

A significant difference was found between 2-S2 and 2-S4, proving that driving behavior can indeed be influenced by auditory feedback. However, results were affected by individual driving styles and the limitations of the driving simulator. Overall, sounds with high valence, low dominance, and clear speed cues, such as 2-S4, show promise for enhancing the driving experience. Sound 2-S8 showed to be unsuitable as a constant driving feedback but could serve as a speed warning above set thresholds.

5. OUTLOOK

We saw that harmonious sounds are perceived as more pleasant and less obtrusive than inharmonic sounds and thus increase driving comfort. Individual preferences for certain sounds and the different driving styles of the limited amount of test participants make it difficult to make generalised statements. We saw, for instance, a significant difference depending on the test subjects' gender in the perception of the sounds in experiment 1. However, it can be stated that there are indications that driving behaviour can be influenced by active sound design. It would be interesting to carry out further investigations based on these findings. Furthermore, familiarisation with the sound of the vehicle is just as important as a willingness to accept and be open to new sounds.

The methodology of the work has strengths and weaknesses: While the iterative approach to sound design provided valuable insights into the interactions between sound and behaviour, the limitations of the sound modding of the driving simulator were a limiting factor. The differences between simulated and real-life conditions are likely to have a particular impact on the emotional perception of the sounds. In the further development of the sounds, the next step would be to equip a test vehicle with the sounds and to test the sounds in real conditions.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank all participants in the experiments.

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